

On-site testing of VOC detectors

Andreas Schütze^{1*}, Sebastian Abegg², Johannes Amann¹, Ulf Struckmeier³, Hendrik Wölper⁴

¹ Saarland University, Saarbrücken, Germany

² Belimo Automation AG, Hinwil, Switzerland

³ ScioSense Germany GmbH, Reutlingen, Germany

⁴ Member of VDI, Düsseldorf/formerly SIEGENIA, Wilnsdorf, Germany

* corresponding author: schuetze@lmt.uni-saarland.de

Table of contents

Abstract	1
1. Introduction: aim and scope	1
1.1 Indoor air quality: relevance and indicators	1
1.2 VOC detectors for IAQ monitoring (including eCO ₂ and AQ indices)	2
2. On-site test protocols for VOC detectors	3
2.1 Ad-hoc or “alive” tests.....	5
2.2 Box test.....	5
2.3 VOC release tests in closed rooms	8
3. Summary and outlook	12
Literature/links	12

Abstract

An increasing number of metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) gas sensors and sensor systems¹ are in use to determine indoor air quality and/or support control of HVAC systems. One benefit of these low-cost MOS gas sensors is, that they are sensitive to a myriad of different volatile organic compounds (VOC). One drawback is that they also react to other gases. Furthermore, chemical properties of many chemical sensors can change during operation due to reversible or irreversible reactions, so drift and poisoning may downgrade the quality of the VOC detector output.

At the start of their operation, VOC detectors will typically work within the manufacturer’s specification and deliver reliable results. But how reliable are the results after months or years of operation under a wide variety of atmospheric conditions? This can only be determined through testing.

Typical calibration procedures require sophisticated and expensive lab equipment, several gases/gas mixtures and many hours or even days. This is neither suitable for end users nor for installed VOC detectors, e.g. in HVAC systems. This paper suggests some test procedures for VOC detectors to check their performance in the field ranging from very simple “alive tests” to more elaborate “VOC release tests” that can provide a relative or, with more effort, even a quantitative assessment for one or more gases at fairly well-defined concentrations even in the field.

1. Introduction: aim and scope

1.1 Indoor air quality: relevance and indicators

Air pollution is one of the main environmental concerns in Europe and worldwide with outside and indoor air contributing similarly to the overall burden of disease according to the EU project Healthvent [1]. Indoor air quality (IAQ) is an important part of indoor environmental quality (IEQ) that relates to comfort, well-being and health of its occupants. IAQ is affected by many parameters, from humidity to

¹ Throughout the text, the term detector is used to denote both individual gas sensor elements as well as sensor systems which may comprise multiple sensors and/or advanced operation and data analysis methods.

particulate matter, volatile organic compounds (VOC) as well as others [2]. With technology becoming cheaper and Internet of Things (IoT) devices being available to a broader public, ubiquitous measurement systems for relevant parameters are in demand.

Humans emit a cocktail of VOC [3, 4] and these are one primary contribution for poor indoor air quality. The sum concentration of all VOC is therefore considered a good indicator for hygienic² assessment of indoor air quality. As early as 1858 Max von Pettenkofer proposed CO₂ as an indicator for VOC emissions by people due to the difficulty of measuring VOC directly at that time, leading to the well-known "Pettenkofer limit" of 1000 ppm³ of CO₂ [5, 6]. CO₂ concentrations show a strong correlation to IAQ but are not the primary cause for poor air quality in typical indoor environments⁴. Nowadays, CO₂ is easy to measure quantitatively and, thus, is often used as proxy for IAQ, especially for demand-controlled ventilation (DCV), as it also offers information about human presence in a room. However, CO₂ measurement does not reflect other VOC sources in indoor air such as emissions from furniture and building materials as well as from human activities like cleaning, cooking [9], or smoking.

The sum concentration of all VOC in indoor air would therefore be a more direct measure for IAQ. Often it is represented by a total volatile organic compound (TVOC) value. Note, however, that due to differences in measurement methods and definitions, there are several different TVOC definitions and most of these do not cover very volatile organic compounds (VVOC) and semi-volatile VOC (SVOC) because they are based on sampling methods [10]. Low-cost VOC sensors are often only calibrated with a few or even one single VOC.

There are international standards for IAQ monitoring, e.g. ISO 16000-1:2004 to aid the planning of indoor pollution monitoring and ISO 16000-6 specifying methods for determination of VOC in indoor air [11]. However, these typically use sorbent sampling tubes (typically Tenax) with subsequent analysis in a laboratory, e.g. by gas chromatography and mass spectrometry (GC/MS). Thus, they are very costly, require trained personnel and are not real-time capable. Furthermore, offline sampling by sorbent tubes limits the quantitative accuracy as well as the detection spectrum to those VOC that are adsorbed on the sampling tube and can be released again by thermal desorption. Many VVOC will simply pass through the sampling material, while most SVOC are not released due to their very high boiling point. Accordingly, results obtained with these analytical sampling methods cannot directly be compared to data obtained by VOC detectors.

1.2 VOC detectors for IAQ monitoring (including eCO₂ and AQ indices)

For IAQ assessment non-dispersive Infrared (NDIR) or photoacoustic sensors for carbon dioxide (CO₂) are the de facto standard today providing reliable and long-term stable results due to the physical measurement principle [12, 13]. CO₂ sensors provide an indirect assessment of IAQ and even the latest MEMS-based photoacoustic sensors have a larger footprint, typically higher power consumption, and are more expensive compared to metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) gas sensors. MOS sensors provide excellent sensitivity and a broad response spectrum covering almost all kinds of VOC [14, 15] and are

² Hygienic assessment addresses comfort and well-being, while health effects are not considered. Assessing the health effect of indoor air requires determination of individual concentrations for critical compounds such as carcinogenic formaldehyde or benzene.

³ Parts per million (ppm) is the unit typically used in the sensor community; more correctly, this corresponds to the mole fraction of one compound, here a VOC or CO₂, in another, here air, with the unit $\mu\text{mol/mol}$. Analytical chemistry usually uses mass per volume, i.e. mg/m^3 or $\mu\text{g/m}^3$.

⁴ Studies have shown health effects of CO₂ itself at concentrations well above (> 5000 ppm) the "Pettenkofer limit", while adverse effects at relevant lower concentrations are ambiguous as many studies do not isolate CO₂ effects from other potential effects such as temperature and influence from other gases. Systematic studies were performed for defining the effective limit value for CO₂ on the international space station ISS, where operational limits are 5000 ppm depending on the duration of the mission and only recent studies suggest lower concentrations of approx. 3000 ppm to already induce first symptoms like headaches [7]. Preliminary evidence indicates potential health risks at CO₂ exposures as low as 1000 ppm and further research is needed to fully understand the potential health effects of chronic or intermittent exposure to indoor air with higher CO₂ concentrations [8].

promising candidates for direct IAQ monitoring [16, 17]. Main drawbacks of many low-cost VOC detectors are their limited long-term stability and potential cross-sensitivity to interfering gases. MOS sensors in particular often show high sensitivity towards other reducing gases like hydrogen (H₂) or carbon monoxide (CO) which could therefore contribute to the measured TVOC or other output value in addition to VOC [18]. Moreover, chemical properties of many chemical sensors can change during long-term operation due to reversible or irreversible reactions, so drift and poisoning is often reported [19]. In indoor air, siloxanes are often found which can induce irreversible changes in the response pattern of MOS sensors [20].

Many commercially available VOC detectors provide a sum signal often designated as total VOC (TVOC) concentration [21] or equivalent CO₂ (eCO₂) concentration [22, 23], the latter to provide an output in the same range as the widely used IR-based CO₂ sensors. Note that VOC, especially MOS, detectors do not show a reaction to CO₂ at relevant indoor concentrations. A third option is to provide an air quality (AQ) index value with an unspecific range of 0 to 500 which is motivated by the U.S. Air Quality Index (AQI) defined and provided by the EPA for various outdoor pollutants⁵.

Thus, while many VOC detectors are available today for IAQ assessment based on VOC, it is very difficult to understand and compare their performance due to different definitions of the output value (TVOC, eCO₂, AQ index) and a lack of standards for VOC detector testing and performance assessment. Note, for example, that ISO 16000-29:2014 “test methods for VOC detectors” actually specifies different specific test methods for assessing the performance of VOC detectors depending on the sensing principle being used and covers only three very specific sensor types.

The draft standard published by VDI/VDE GMA [25] aims to achieve the comparability of different VOC detectors by proposing a technology-agnostic test scheme for the performance of IAQ detectors based on VOC as well as a novel AQ index intended to be used by various manufacturers. However, the proposed test scheme requires advanced lab equipment allowing exact exposure to various test gases as well as testing of the response under various atmospheric conditions, i.e. temperature and especially humidity as an important interferent for gas sensors. Suitable test set-ups have been described in literature [26, 27]. For the diverse VOC present in indoor atmosphere, the main challenge is the high complexity of the gas mixtures in real environments with several hundred components [28, 29], which even in the most complex test systems can only be approximated to a certain degree [30]. While lab calibration offers the highest accuracy, it is limited as it measures in clean air with a limited spectrum of test gases and cannot reflect the complex variations of the background and various VOC occurring in real environments.

This is further exacerbated by dynamic sensor operation to improve the VOC detector performance and/or by advanced data analysis or AI methods which are employed to transform the recorded raw sensor data into an abstract AQ output value. This data treatment can include filtering or smoothing of the data to fit the application. In many typical indoor situations AQ will change slowly, on the order of 10 min, so a VOC detector does not need to show a fast response to a challenge.

2. On-site test protocols for VOC detectors

This contribution discusses on-site test protocols intended for end users who want to check and compare the performance of VOC detectors on their own and with limited effort in terms of test complexity. In fact, there are various methods ranging from very simple, similar to breathing over a CO₂ sensor to observe the reaction to CO₂ in exhaled breath, to increasingly complicated based on the availability of test equipment and also the experience of the person performing the test, cf. Fig. 1.

⁵ This AQI provides a common color/grade scale for the five major pollutants contributing to outdoor air quality, i.e., particulate matter (PM), ozone, carbon monoxide, nitrogen dioxide and sulfur dioxide to allow a comparison of their respective contribution to the overall air quality. For further information cf. [24]

The necessity for on-site tests can be manifold. One aspect is that local variations in background atmosphere can have an influence on the VOC detector performance, so testing under the specific conditions of an installation is of interest. Second, sensor degradation over time, for example due to drift or poisoning, could degrade the performance. Finally, humans have only limited ability to grasp IAQ with their senses. Thus, having the possibility to simply check the VOC detector performance can help to increase trust and confidence in the systems.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram to categorize different test methods: complexity in terms of equipment required and experience of experimenter vs. informative value (“quality”), i.e. level of confidence and/or accuracy.

On the other hand, seemingly simple tests can have negative consequences. For example, it might seem a good idea to check the response of a VOC detector using a lighter to release isobutane or some alcoholic drink to expose the detector to ethanol, similar to breathing over a CO₂ sensor. But one should be aware that VOC target concentrations are very low with typical levels for increased ventilation⁶ starting at 1 mg/m³ corresponding to approx. 0.5 ppm depending on the specific VOC. Compared to CO₂ with a target concentration for increased ventilation of 1,000 ppm this is a difference of more than three orders of magnitude, thus VOC detectors for IAQ monitoring are optimized for high sensitivity, making them susceptible to overload in many scenarios. When testing with a butane lighter, concentrations in the high % range corresponding to more than 100,000 ppm can easily be reached; similarly, the ethanol concentration above an alcoholic beverage is many orders of magnitude higher than the VOC concentration in typical indoor situations and the breath alcohol level after a single beer is typically between 150 and 250 ppm. Thus, these simple tests result in a drastic overload for IAQ VOC detectors which will at least “blind” them for some time. Often, this may even result in irreversible changes due to processes on the sensor surface occurring at very high concentrations, basically severely damaging or even destroying the VOC detector for the intended application.

DON'T challenge an IAQ VOC detector with

- a lighter
- spray disinfectant
- deodorant spray or perfume
- hair spray, waterproofing spray

as this will overload the sensor dramatically, like weighing a truck on your kitchen scale.

⁶ The common assumption is that IAQ is improved with increased ventilation although poor outside air might actually decrease IAQ.

In the following, different on-site tests are described allowing users to perform tests according to their requirements, i.e. from a simple “alive” check to more quantitative tests such as release tests in a small test chamber or, more realistically, in a normal room with constant background, and according to their expertise and available equipment. Note that test procedures are also suggested by some sensor manufacturers [31].

2.1 Ad-hoc or “alive” tests

There are several simple methods to challenge a VOC detector to determine if it is still “alive”, i.e., will change its output in dependence of the ambient atmosphere.

- **Breath test:** similar to CO₂ sensors, breathing over a VOC detector should result in a reaction, typically indicating a lower air quality due to the VOC in exhaled breath. In contrast to CO₂ sensors, where the response will be similar due to a fairly stable CO₂ concentration in exhaled breath of 4 %, the response of VOC detectors can be minute or very strong, depending on the specific sensor type, but mostly on the breath composition, which changes strongly depending on diet, personal hygiene etc.
- **Marker pen test:** typical marker pens are solvent based and will emit low concentrations when the cap is removed and the pen is waved in front of the VOC detector. Again, the response depends strongly on the type of pen and will also change with the age of the pen and with ambient temperature.
- **Drinks test:** most IAQ detectors can be tested with drinks, especially sparkling mineral water (CO₂), fruit juice (low concentration of alcohol), beer (CO₂ and alcohol) or wine and spirits (high concentration of alcohol)⁷. By partially filling a glass and placing the detector above the glass it is exposed to the headspace, i.e., the gas atmosphere above the liquid. VOC detectors should react only to alcohol (and some other VOC at lower concentration), but not to CO₂ alone, i.e. sparkling mineral water. A true CO₂ sensor will only react to CO₂, i.e. will show no reaction to fruit juice and other drinks without fizz. An eCO₂ sensor, on the other hand, will react like a VOC sensor.
- For mobile, battery-powered VOC detectors, simply changing the ambient⁸, e.g. going from a room with high occupancy to a room with low occupancy or outside, should also result in a change of the sensor signal. However, this is sometimes difficult to interpret correctly: For example, a room with many people inside might be well ventilated and, thus, have a lower VOC concentration than a room with few people which has recently been cleaned and thus contaminated with higher VOC levels from cleaning agents.

While these ad-hoc tests should be able to show that the detector reacts to the ambient atmosphere, they do not allow to judge the performance of VOC detectors or compare different detectors due to the many unknowns (gas type, gas concentration, ambient conditions). Furthermore, even if a VOC detector does not show a reaction to a challenge like breathing this is not necessarily an indication that the sensor is not working correctly, as the detector might be designed with a low-pass filter to smooth the response as IAQ in a room will change only slowly in normal situations.

Installed VOC detectors, e.g. in a light fixture or even in the ventilation system itself, are even more difficult to challenge as the sensor might not be reachable and the housing etc. could further dilute the concentration and slow down the response.

2.2 Box test

Evaluation kits and small products can be tested in clean food-grade containers such as cookie tins or food-grade plastic boxes. The VOC detector is placed inside the closed box and a very small volume of

⁷ Note again, that concentrations in the headspace of alcoholic drinks are very high and might overload or even destroy VOC detectors.

⁸ Mainly applicable for battery powered sensor systems, others might reset after power-off resulting in an offset.

ethanol (or another VOC) vapor from the headspace of an ethanol-filled vial is injected via a small hole in the lid using a commercial syringe. The hole is then covered with a piece of tape and once the signal has reached equilibrium, the signal value can be recorded. After removing the lid, the signal should return to its original baseline value and the process can be repeated. Fig. 2 shows how this method allows the experimenter to “switch” between background and different signal levels, depending on injected volume. An internal fan can be used to achieve fast equilibration.

Fig. 2: Example for a sequence of ethanol exposures in a small test chamber. The sensor response alternates between baseline (corresponding to background room air) and different signal levels (corresponding to ethanol injections).

The setup shown in Fig. 3 consists of a 14.3 l plastic box with an internal fan and a lid. The experiment is conducted in a well-ventilated office. Small volumes (0.1 ml, 0.2 ml, and 0.4 ml) of ethanol headspace are drawn from a vial filled with pure ethanol with a septum cap. The vial should only be touched briefly to minimize heat transfer from the hand to the liquid. The septum ensures that the vapor pressure inside the vial stays constant. The volumes are then injected into the box as described above.

Fig. 3: Example for a setup for ethanol exposures. a) Food-grade plastic box with lid and internal fan. b) Drawing ethanol vapor from the headspace of ethanol in a vial with septum cap.

The ethanol concentration $c_{Ethanol}$ in the box can be calculated from the volume of the box V_{box} , volume of the injected vapor V_{inj} , ambient pressure $p_{ambient}$ and the literature value of ethanol vapor pressure $p_{Ethanol}$ at the given room temperature:

$$c_{Ethanol} = \frac{p_{Ethanol}}{p_{ambient}} \cdot \frac{V_{inj}}{V_{box}} \quad (1)$$

The experiment shown here was performed at 25 °C, so $p_{Ethanol} = 7.9 \text{ kPa}$ [32]. Considering the injected volumes and the volume of the box, ethanol concentrations are approx. 0.5, 1 and 2 ppm, respectively. The uncertainty of the ethanol concentration is dominated by the uncertainty of the temperature measurement and the accuracy of the injected volume using a commercial 1 ml syringe. Repeatability will depend significantly on the skill and experience of the experimenter and on the temperature control in the room.

Fig. 4 shows the corresponding resistance measurements of a commercial MOS sensor element (one hotplate of a ScioSense ENS161 in standard operating mode [33]).

Fig. 4: Ethanol concentrations and corresponding sensor resistance for the box test.

Despite the primitive nature of the experiment, key features of correct sensor performance can be observed:

- The sensor's resistance responds rapidly whenever the stimulus is applied (ethanol injection) and released (venting the box). This confirms the sensor's short response time.
- After each stimulus, the sensor's resistance reading returns to a baseline corresponding to the room's background VOC levels. Over time, there is typically some variation in the baseline resistance reading (here: between 30 and 32 kOhm) as the air quality in the room slowly changes. However, this variation is small compared to the effect of the ethanol stimuli. The fact that the sensor reliably returns to its baseline resistance confirms that it does not suffer any "memory effects" or damage by the ethanol exposure.
- Generally, the sensor response (in this case a decrease in sensor resistance) is proportional to the ethanol concentration. Some variation will be observed; this is predominantly caused by experimental error. Note that, as room temperature changes throughout the day, the ethanol headspace concentration in the vial changes. In the range between 20 and 30 °C, ethanol vapor pressure changes by almost a factor of 2 [32], so the contribution of temperature to the amount of injected ethanol is substantial. If room temperature fluctuates too much, a thermostat may be required.
- Sensor signals are not perfectly rectangular:
 - Sometimes there is a spike at the beginning of an injection. This is caused by a temporary higher level of ethanol close to the sensor at the beginning of the injection. However, this disperses quickly, especially if a fan is employed.

- Due to minor leaks from the box to the room, ethanol will escape from the closed box. Consequently, the sensor signal will change slightly even when the lid is closed.

When plotting sensor resistance vs. ethanol concentration (Fig. 5), one can see:

- The spread of datapoints is much higher when ethanol is injected and much smaller when background air (0 ppm of additional ethanol) is measured:
 - The spread in background air results from slow, natural changes in the room's background VOC level. If the room is well ventilated, the room's VOC level is not affected by the experiment.
 - The spread during injections, however, results primarily from the experimental error (both injected volume and change in room temperature) and is thus much larger.
- At low ethanol concentrations, the graph follows a power law [34]. At higher levels (> 2 ppm), however, the sensor may gradually start saturating and the graph may deviate from linear in this semi-logarithmic plot.

Fig. 5: Correlation between sensor resistance and (nominal) ethanol concentration. The large spread in the data points is predominantly caused by experimental error owing to the relatively primitive setup.

Note that these observations can be expected when looking at the raw data output of the sensor, in this case resistance. However, a rapid succession of many medium to high level stimuli in a small volume is not typical for most indoor air applications. Consequently, built-in algorithms which process and interpret raw signals in the context of typical indoor air applications may fail to give reasonable TVOC or eCO₂ estimates under the conditions of this experiment. Hence, this type of experiment is unsuitable for testing VOC detectors with TVOC or eCO₂ outputs. It can, however, be used to test the fundamental performance of a sensor element as seen in the raw data.

2.3 VOC release tests in closed rooms

Preliminary considerations

VOC detectors can be tested directly at their place of installation by releasing VOC in the corresponding indoor room. Therefore, the room in which the detector is placed has to be characterized and there are a few things to keep in mind:

- The (free) volume of the room is required to calculate the theoretically released concentration. For a valid and reproducible measurement, the room needs a certain air tightness. This means

that doors and windows should be closed during the release test, HVAC systems should be switched off as they also interfere with the desired release test. Note, that a fully sealed room with zero air exchange is unrealistic as window and door seals always show some leakage. In addition, the building materials and furnishings should be considered as they can cause significant VOC emissions, especially for a newly renovated room and new furniture. It is also recommended to avoid other non-room specific VOC sources such as open food, drinks, open waste containers, other liquids, cosmetics, cleaning or cooking processes, printing, etc.

- Although VOC and other gases quickly disperse homogeneously in a room, the VOC detector to be tested should be placed as centrally as possible in the room. In any case, placement behind objects as well as close to doors and windows should be avoided. If possible, a fan should be used to ensure fast and even distribution of the VOC during the release experiment.
- The room should be ventilated before the release test for at least 15 minutes with maximum air exchange, i.e. by opening doors and windows where possible⁹. Then, doors and windows should be closed to allow the room to equilibrate for at least 30 min during which the VOC detector should already be turned on to allow warm-up (please observe manufacturer recommendations for run-in procedure, where applicable).
- It is advised to perform a reference experiment for several hours without releasing VOC and without the presence of people. The VOC detector reading should stay fairly constant during this experiment, i.e., change by less than 20%, indicating neither increase due to emission sources nor decrease due to air exchange after previous exposures.

Release tests

Release tests should be performed without human presence as much as possible as humans also emit VOC due to their metabolism, but also from cosmetics and hygiene products. Thus, the room should be entered only when absolutely necessary. Ideally, the room should only be entered briefly to start the release test and for ventilation after the release test is completed. The VOC detector read-out should be observed or recorded during the entire release test, e.g., using a data recorder or by observing the display with a webcam.

Ethanol, isopropanol (hand sanitizer), acetone, toluene, xylene, ethyl acetate are typical VOC to which IAQ VOC detectors should react and which are easily available, simple to handle in liquid form and harmless in concentrations up to 10 ppm in air. If other VOC are of interest, these can also be used.

Recommended concentrations for release tests should be in the range between 500 ppb and 10 ppm as, depending on the VOC and the VOC detector. Lower concentrations are very difficult to measure in such a setup and higher concentrations can irreversibly damage the VOC detector, see above. In any case, this covers the relevant concentration range for IAQ as concentrations below 0.3 mg/m³ (corresponding to 122 ppb for isopropanol and 80 ppb for toluene) are deemed hygienically harmless, increased ventilation is recommended starting typically at 1 mg/m³ (~407 ppb and 265 ppb for isopropanol and toluene, respectively) and concentrations above 10 mg/m³ (~4 ppm and 2.7 ppm for isopropanol and toluene, respectively) are deemed unacceptable [35]. To avoid a higher-than-average concentration at the detector, the VOC source should be placed at least 2 m from the VOC detector. To achieve a reliable and reproducible VOC release, two methods can be used.

Method 1: Evaporation of liquids requiring only minimal equipment

VOC release tests are performed simply via evaporation of a certain volume of the target VOC in liquid form. The desired increase in concentration in terms of mg/m³ due to the release test is easily calculated from the room volume, i.e., in a room with a free volume of 50 m³ and a desired target concentration of 5 mg/m³ a total of 250 mg should be released. Note that this corresponds to a liquid

⁹ Note that external sources should be avoided as much as possible, i.e. traffic and construction work in a city, fertilization with manure in the country, etc.

volume of approx. ¼ ml, again indicating the high sensitivity required for IAQ VOC detectors. Similarly, the desired concentration in ppm can be calculated using equations (2) and (3):

$$c_{target} = \frac{m_{VOC}}{M_{VOC}} \cdot \frac{0.0245 \text{ m}^3 / \text{mol}}{V_{room}} \quad (2)$$

Here, m_{VOC} is the mass of the released VOC (in g), M_{VOC} is the molecular weight (in g/mol), and V_{room} is the free room volume. At standard conditions (1 atm, 25 °C) 1 mol corresponds to 24.5 l or 0.0245 m³. Since the required small volumes (a few ml) are easily dosed using a small syringe, equation (3) uses the liquid VOC volume V_{VOC} (in ml) and the density ρ_{VOC} (in g/ml) to calculate the weight m_{VOC} of the VOC (in g).

$$m_{VOC} = V_{VOC} \cdot \rho_{VOC} \quad (3)$$

Note that the calculated concentration according to equation (2) is a theoretical value assuming homogeneous distribution in a sealed room without air exchange and without background. If the VOC is already present in the background, the calculated value would correspond to the increase of the concentration during the release test above the background value.

Uncertainties cannot be avoided, e.g. in the determination of the free room volume or unknown background concentrations, but the biggest uncertainty contributions result from the exact dosage of the VOC (either as mass or volume) and from handling the liquid. A surface with slightly elevated temperature is recommended to ensure fast evaporation of the liquid. Note however, that the temperature should not induce any reactions as this would change the gas composition and the resulting concentration.

During the experiment, a slow decay of the VOC concentration will result from unavoidable air exchange as well as adsorption of the VOC on surfaces and reaction processes. Fig. 6 shows the response of a highly accurate VOC detector compared to two reference instruments. All show the same temporal behavior, i.e., a fast increase during VOC release followed by a slow decrease of the concentration. The peak of the recorded concentration corresponds to the calculated target concentration c_{target} (~600 ppb ± 10%) if the VOC detector has a sufficiently fast response time and is placed sufficiently far from the release location.

Fig. 6: Recorded concentrations after release of 0.164 ml Toluene in an office with 62 m³ free volume for a high-performance VOC detector system (red), an online GC-PID detector system (purple dots) and offline GC-MS analysis after sampling (yellow dots) [16]. The tested VOC detector provides a reading approx. every 2.5 min.

Method 2: Controlled flow from a gas cylinder requiring complex equipment

A second approach requiring more complex equipment is based on test gas cylinders containing a defined concentration of one or more VOC. Suitable test gas cylinder concentrations are in the range between 1,000 and 10,000 ppm as lower concentrations will require a long time to achieve relevant target concentrations, higher concentrations are difficult to control (in a room with 50 m³ a test gas cylinder with 10,000 ppm achieves a target concentration of 1 ppm by releasing 5 l of test gas). The release is controlled, e.g. by filling a balloon with the target volume outside of the room and releasing the gas inside the room or, more accurately, using a mass flow controller. Mass flow controllers and certified test gas cylinders allow very accurate control of the released VOC amount with low uncertainty, down to < 1 %, thus the total uncertainty is probably dominated by the uncertainty of the free room volume and unknown background concentrations.

This second method extends the possible spectrum of test gases also to VVOC and, more importantly, to permanent gases such as hydrogen or methane.

In principle, analytical reference measurements can be performed in parallel to both methods at the same location as the VOC detector to validate the release [17]. Note, however, that the uncertainty of typical reference methods, e.g. sampling on Tenax, followed by lab analysis with gas chromatography and mass spectrometry, is often in the order of 25 %, mostly due to uncertainties caused by the sampling process. Thus, under well-controlled conditions the calculated concentration can offer a better absolute reference. Tests based on either method can also be combined or extended, e.g. by subsequent or parallel release of various VOC or various amounts. This allows an estimation if the detector provides a linear response and constant sensitivity vs. various VOC. In fact, under well controlled and near ideal test conditions these release tests can allow a fairly accurate quantitative on-site testing of VOC detectors.

Note that the decay curve recorded by a (linear) online monitor offers the potential of estimating the air exchange rate of a room based on the slope of the initial concentration decrease, cf. Fig. 7. This can help to evaluate the air tightness of a room, but also the efficiency of a ventilation system.

Fig. 7: Recorded decrease of the ethanol concentration in a closed room after a release test. From the initial slope the decay rate can be estimated, here approx. 0.95 per hour. Note that, especially when using VOC with low vapor pressure, this decay can also reflect other effects, e.g. adsorption on surfaces, in addition to the air exchange rate of the room.

3. Summary and outlook

This contribution describes various on-site test protocols intended for end users who want to check and compare the performance of VOC detectors on their own and with limited effort in terms of test complexity. Note that a true test of the performance of VOC detectors for IAQ assessment requires complex lab equipment and relies on a well-defined test procedure as outlined in the draft guideline VDI/VDE 3518 part 4 [25].

This paper is intended as a basis for discussion and exchange of experiences between VOC detector manufacturers, researchers and end users and can be extended to include further test protocols. If you are interested in contributing to this concept, please contact Andreas Schütze via email: (schuetze@lmt.uni-saarland.de).

Literature/links

- [1] A. Asikainen, P. Carrer, S. Kephelopoulou, E.D.O. Fernandes, P. Wargocki, O. Hänninen: Reducing burden of disease from residential indoor air exposures in Europe (HEALTHVENT project). *Environ. Health* 2016, 15, S35, doi: 10.1186/s12940-016-0101-8
- [2] W. A. Spaul: Building-related factors to consider in indoor air quality evaluations. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.* 1994, 94, 385–389, doi: 10.1053/ai.1994.v94.a56020
- [3] S. Herberger, M. Herold, H. Ulmer, A. Burdack-Freitag, F. Mayer: Detection of human effluents by a MOS gas sensor in correlation to VOC quantification by GC/MS. *Build. Environ.* 2010, 45, 2430–2439, doi: 10.1016/j.buildenv.2010.05.005
- [4] B. Buszewski, M. Keszy, T. Ligor, A. Amann: Human exhaled air analytics: Biomarkers of diseases. *Biomed. Chromatogr.* 2007, 21, 553–566, doi: 10.1002/bmc.835
- [5] M. Pettenkofer: Über den Luftwechsel in Wohngebäuden; Literarisch-Artistische Anstalt der J.G. Cotta'schen Buchhandlung. 1858. Available online (accessed on 17 May 2021): <https://opacplus.bsb-muenchen.de/title/BV013009721>
- [6] Bundesgesundheitsamt: Gesundheitliche Bewertung von Kohlendioxid in der Innenraumluft, *Bundesgesundheitsblatt, Gesundheitsforschung, Gesundheitsschutz* 2008, 51:1358–1369, doi: 10.1007/s00103-008-0707-2
- [7] J. Law, M Van Baalen, M. Foy, S.S. Mason, C. Mendez, W.L. Wear: Relationship Between Carbon Dioxide Levels and Reported Headaches on the International Space Station, *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine* (2014) 56(5), 477-483, doi: 10.1097/JOM.0000000000000158
- [8] T.A. Jacobson, J.S. Kler, M.T. Hernke, R.K. Braun, K.C. Meyer, W.E. Funk: Direct human health risks of increased atmospheric carbon dioxide, *Nature Sustainability* 2019, 2, pp. 691–701, doi: 10.1038/s41893-019-0323-1.
- [9] Y. Liu, P.K. Misztal, J. Xiong, Y. Tian, C. Arata, R.J. Weber, W.W. Nazaroff, A.H. Goldstein: Characterizing sources and emissions of volatile organic compounds in a northern California residence using space- and time-resolved measurements. *Indoor Air* 2019, 29, 630–644, doi: 10.1111/ina.12562
- [10] T. Salthammer: TVOC – Revisited, *Environment International* 167, 107440, doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2022.107440
- [11] International Organization for Standardization. *Indoor Air - Part 6: Determination of volatile organic compounds in indoor and test chamber air by active sampling Tenax TA(R) sorbent, thermal desorption and gas chromatography using MS/FID (ISO 16000-6.2011)*. ISO 16000-6. 2011
- [12] S.K. Pandey, K.-H. Kim: The Relative Performance of NDIR-based Sensors in the Near Real-time Analysis of CO₂ in Air. *Sensors* 2007, 7, 1683-1696, doi: 10.3390/s7091683
- [13] S. Palzer: Photoacoustic-Based Gas Sensing: A Review, *Sensors* 2020, 20(9), 2745; doi: 10.3390/s20092745
- [14] M.J. Madou, S.R. Morrison: *Chemical Sensing with Solid State Devices*; Academic Press, Inc.: San Diego, CA, USA, 1989; ISBN 978-0-12-464965-1.
- [15] N. Bârsan, U. Weimar: Understanding the fundamental principles of metal oxide based gas sensors; the example of CO sensing with SnO₂ sensors in the presence of humidity. *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* 2003, 15, 813–839, doi: 10.1088/0953-8984/15/20/201
- [16] A. Schütze, T. Sauerwald: Indoor air quality monitoring, in: Eduard Llobet (ed.): *Advanced Nanomaterials for Inexpensive Gas Microsensors*, Elsevier, 2020, Pages 209-234, ISBN: 978-0-12-814827-3, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-814827-3.00011-6
- [17] T. Baur, J. Amann, C. Schultealbert, A. Schütze: Field Study of Metal Oxide Semiconductor Gas Sensors in Temperature Cycled Operation for Selective VOC Monitoring in Indoor Air, *Atmosphere* (2021) 12, 647, doi: 10.3390/atmos12050647

- [18] C. Schultealbert, T. Baur, A. Schütze, T. Sauerwald: Facile Quantification and Identification Techniques for Reducing Gases over a Wide Concentration Range Using a MOS Sensor in Temperature-Cycled Operation. *Sensors* 2018, 18, 744, doi: 10.3390/s18030744
- [19] G. Korotcenkov, B.K. Cho: Instability of metal oxide-based conductometric gas sensors and approaches to stability improvement (short survey). *Sens. Actuators B* 2011, 156, 527–538, doi: 10.1016/J.SNB.2011.02.024
- [20] C. Schultealbert, I. Uzun, T. Baur, T. Sauerwald, A. Schütze: Siloxane treatment of metal oxide semiconductor gas sensors in temperature-cycled operation – sensitivity and selectivity, *J. Sens. Syst.* (2020) 9, 283-292, doi: 10.5194/jsss-9-283-2020
- [21] D. Ruffer, F. Hoehne, J. Bühler: New digital metal-oxide (MOx) sensor platform. *Sensors* 2018, 18, 1052, doi: 10.3390/s18041052
- [22] S. Herberger, M. Herold, H. Ulmer: MOS gas sensor technology for demand controlled ventilation, 30th AIVC Conference "Trends in High Performance Buildings and the Role of Ventilation", Berlin, Germany, 1-2 October 2009
- [23] Bosch Sensortec GmbH, BME688 data sheet, page 31: <https://www.bosch-sensortec.com/media/boschsensortec/downloads/datasheets/bst-bme688-ds000.pdf>
- [24] Technical Assistance Document for the Reporting of Daily Air Quality – the Air Quality Index (AQI) <https://www.airnow.gov/sites/default/files/2020-05/aqi-technical-assistance-document-sept2018.pdf>
- [25] VDI/VDE 3518 Part 4:2023-XX – Draft Multigas sensors; Standardized test instructions and test gases for VOC detectors for indoor air quality measurement (Entwurf Multigassensoren; Standardisierte Prüfanweisung und Prüfgase für VOC-Detektoren zur Innenraumlufgütemessung), Beuth Verlag, Berlin
- [26] N. Helwig, M. Schüler, C. Bur, A. Schütze, T. Sauerwald: Gas mixing apparatus for automated gas sensor characterization, *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 25 (2014) 055903, doi: 10.1088/0957-0233/25/5/055903
- [27] M. Leidinger, C. Schultealbert, J. Neu, A. Schütze, T. Sauerwald: Characterization and calibration of gas sensor systems at ppb level - a versatile test gas generation system, *IOP Measurement Science and Technology* 29 (2018), 015901, doi: 10.1088/1361-6501/aa91da
- [28] H. Hofmann, P. Plieninger: Bereitstellung einer Datenbank zum Vorkommen von flüchtigen organischen Verbindungen in der Raumluft, (2008). Available via (13.05.2023): <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/publikation/long/3637.pdf>
- [29] H. Hofmann, G. Erdmann, A. Müller: Zielkonflikt energieeffiziente Bauweise und gute Raumluftqualität – Datenerhebung für flüchtige organische Verbindungen in der Innenraumluft von Wohn- und Bürogebäuden (Lösungswege), (2014). Available via (13.05.2023): https://www.agoef.de/fileadmin/user_upload/dokumente/forschung/AGOEF-Abschlussbericht_VOC_DB_II-barrierefrei.pdf
- [30] D. Arendes, J. Amann, C. Tessier, O. Brieger, A. Schütze, C. Bur: Qualification and Optimisation of a Gas Mixing Apparatus for Complex Trace Gas Mixtures, *tm – Technisches Messen*, 2023, aop, doi: 10.1515/teme-2023-0075
- [31] Sensirion AG; Stäfa, Switzerland, https://sensirion.com/media/documents/69323F20/618CF28B/Sensirion_Gas_Sensors_SGP40_Quick_Testing_Guide_D1.pdf
- [32] Dortmund Data Bank, DDBST GmbH, http://www.ddbst.de/en/EED/PCP/VAP_C11.php
- [33] ScioSense, ENS161 datasheet, <https://www.sciosense.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/SC-001855-DS-2-ENS161-Datasheet.pdf>
- [34] N. Yamazoe, K. Shimanoe: Theory of power laws for semiconductor gas sensors, *Sens. Actuators B* 2008, 128 (2), 566-573, doi: 10.1016/J.SNB.2007.07.036
- [35] Umweltbundesamt: Beurteilung von Innenraumlufkontaminationen mittels Referenz- und Richtwerten, *Bundesgesundheitsblatt - Gesundheitsforschung - Gesundheitsschutz* 2007 · 50:990–1005, doi: 10.1007/s00103-007-0290-y